

PREVALENCE OF LEFT VENTRICULAR DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH COPD

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Abstract

Background

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and left ventricular dysfunction (LVD) frequently coexist, causing significant morbidity and mortality. The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of LVD in patients with COPD.

Methods

The cross-sectional study included a total of 200 participants: 100 COPD patients without any apparent cardiovascular disease and 100 controls. Patients were assessed using ECG tracing, spirometry, and transthoracic echocardiography which include both standard and tissue Doppler techniques. LV function was measured using LV ejection fraction (LVEF), E/A ratio, E/e' ratio, left atrial volume index (LAVI), and peak velocity of tricuspid regurgitation (TR). All participants were analyzed based on their respiratory and left ventricular function findings.

Results

Prevalence of left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD) was 21% in COPD patients as compared to 6% in controls ($p = 0.003$). Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) also differed considerably between the two, with 42% of COPD patients and 19% of controls presenting with LVDD ($p < 0.001$). FEV₁ was found to be inversely correlated to LVEF ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.01$) and positively correlated with GOLD stage ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$). LVD was an independent predictor of COPD (OR: 3.67; 95% CI 1.74–7.76, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion

The prevalence of LVD was significantly greater in COPD patients, especially with increased disease progression. Performing routine cardiac screening in COPD patients can help prevent and treat coexisting LVD and improve disease outcome.

INTRODUCTION

COPD is a chronic progressive lung disease characterized by persistent airflow obstruction and respiratory symptoms.¹ It is the fourth most common cause of death worldwide and represents a substantial economic and social burden.² COPD

encompasses a number of diseases including chronic bronchitis, emphysema, and chronic asthmatic bronchitis.³ It has now become widely accepted that COPD is not only a pulmonary disease but also a systemic inflammatory

disease. With effects on many extrapulmonary systems, particularly in its later stages, COPD can often be associated with skeletal muscle dysfunction, osteoporosis, increased risk of atherosclerotic vascular disease, weight loss, depression, anxiety, and more.⁴

COPD and cardiovascular disease are among the leading causes of global morbidity and mortality.² It is suggested that 20-70% of patients with COPD present with some degree of cardiovascular disease. COPD is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease.⁵ The pathophysiological mechanisms in this association are related to systemic inflammation, chronic hypoxia, arterial stiffness, pulmonary hypertension, oxidative stress, ventricular coupling, and subendocardial ischemia.^{6,7} This can lead to the development of left ventricular dysfunction (LVD), as airflow obstruction and lung hyperinflation can reduce left ventricular diastolic filling and cardiac chamber size.⁸ The concomitant presence of both worsens disease outcomes and survival. Due to a broad overlap of symptoms, including dyspnea and fatigue, the clinical diagnosis is often challenging and LVD is frequently misdiagnosed. Smoking and aging are major risk factors of COPD and a number of other morbidities, including LVD. Consequently, the prevalence of both COPD and LVD is high among adult smokers.^{9,10}

Despite advancements in medical research and health care efforts, COPD continues to show an upward rise in mortality.¹¹ There is an increased risk of mortality in patients with COPD exacerbations and comorbidities, including LVD. These patients can have both systolic and diastolic abnormalities without overt cardiovascular disease.^{12,13} Understanding this association is important, mortality and cardiovascular hospitalization in patients with COPD may be improved by optimization of therapies in those with coexisting LVD. All patients with COPD should be regularly assessed for cardiac and pulmonary function by echocardiography and pulmonary function tests to avoid misdiagnosis and treatment.

The aim of our study is to evaluate the prevalence of left ventricular dysfunction in patients with

chronic obstructive lung disease and to identify associated clinical and demographic factors.

Methods

Study Population

In this cross-sectional study, we enrolled 100 patients with uncomplicated COPD from the Department of Pulmonology at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan. A control group of 100 participants was selected from patients' companions after basic screening for their general health and obtaining normal spirometry results. All 200 participants had to be 40 years and older and recruitment was carried out using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

The study was conducted for a period of 12 months. The diagnosis of COPD was made according to the Global Initiative for Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) guidelines, with each patient having a post-bronchodilator FEV₁/FVC < 0.70. Those who had a previous history of heart failure or structural heart disease including myocardial infarction and cardiomyopathy were not enrolled in the study. Participants with comorbidities such as unmanageable hypertension (resting blood pressure > 180/110 mmHg) and/or diabetes (HbA1c > 9%) were also not included. Using medication that could alter cardiac function (beta blockers, calcium channel blockers (CCBs), digoxin, and antiarrhythmic drugs) was considered an exclusion criterion. This study was carried out in accordance with institutional and international ethical standards. Written informed consents were obtained from all participants.

Data Collection

All participants underwent resting electrocardiogram (ECG) tracing, systolic and diastolic blood pressure measurements, pulmonary function testing, and transthoracic echocardiography including standard and tissue Doppler techniques. Pulmonary function was assessed by performing standardized spirometry to measure forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁), forced vital capacity (FVC), and FEV₁/FVC ratio. COPD diagnosis was defined as FEV₁/FVC < 0.70 and no post-bronchodilator reversibility of FEV₁. The severity of disease was

classified according to the latest GOLD staging system. In the COPD patient group, arterial oxygen blood partial pressure (PaO_2) and carbon blood partial pressure (PaCO_2) were measured to get an arterial blood analysis.

Cardiac function was evaluated by transthoracic echocardiography based on apical four- and two-chamber imaging planes. All echocardiograms were conducted by certified sonographers in the Department of Cardiology at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan. Left ventricular systolic function was assessed using two-dimensional imaging by the biplane Simpson's method measuring the shortening fraction (FS%), left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), followed by tissue Doppler imaging (TDI) to obtain myocardial velocity (s') at the mitral annulus. LVSD was defined as having a LVEF $< 50\%$. Left ventricular diastolic function was assessed through a more multiparametric approach based on the American Society of Echocardiogram (ASE). This included pulsed-wave Doppler of mitral inflow velocities (E and A waves), early relaxation velocity (e') using TDI, and calculated E/e' velocity ratio. Additional parameters were left atrial volume index (LAVI), and peak velocity of tricuspid regurgitation (TR). LVDD was defined as having a E/A ratio < 0.8 or > 2.0 , or E/e' ratio > 14 .

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to evaluate patient characteristics within the study. The data was stratified by COPD status as COPD participants and non-COPD participants. Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The results obtained in the COPD group and in the control group were compared using chi-square tests. This included the prevalence of LVD between the two groups. Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients were used to analyze the association of COPD severity and cardiac function parameters such as LVEF. A multivariate logistic regression model with the 95% confidence

interval (CI) was employed to investigate the relationship between the data obtained. This included the association between COPD severity and prevalence of LVEF. Demographic variables that could alter the data were adjusted for more accuracy. All statistical calculations were done using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 26 (IBM Corp.), and a p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study with a total of 200 participants. Participants were classified into two groups, one group consisting of 100 participants with COPD, while the other group had 100 participants without COPD. COPD participants had a mean age of 64.3 ± 9.2 years, while the controls had a mean age of 62.7 ± 8.7 years. Both groups had no significant difference with respect to age ($p = 0.18$). The COPD group was 76% males, whereas 72% of controls were males. Similarly, both groups had no significant difference in gender distribution ($p = 0.53$). Participants from the control group had a higher mean BMI ($25.4 \pm 4.1 \text{ kg/m}^2$) compared to that of the COPD group ($22.1 \pm 3.6 \text{ kg/m}^2$; $p < 0.001$). A statistically significant higher frequency of smoking was recorded in the COPD group (35.8 ± 12.4) in contrast to the control group (14.7 ± 9.1).

COPD Severity and Pulmonary Function

We classified the severity of COPD using the GOLD staging system and found that of the total number of COPD patients; 18% had Stage I, 36% had Stage II, 32% had Stage III, and 14% had Stage IV. These patients presented with mean FEV_1 of $49.2 \pm 15.7\%$ of predicted values and mean FVC of $64.8 \pm 13.2\%$ of predicted values, as shown in Figure 1. There was a strong negative correlation between FEV_1 and GOLD stage ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.001$), as lung function continued to decline with increased COPD severity.

Figure 1. Relationship Between GOLD Stages and Pulmonary Function.
 Abbreviations: GOLD, Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease

Left Ventricular Systolic Dysfunction

There was a significantly higher number of participants with LVEF < 50% in the COPD group compared to the control group (21% vs. 6%; p value = 0.003). The COPD patients also had a lower mean LVEF (52.7 ± 7.3%) than the

control group (58.9 ± 6.1%; p < 0.001). COPD patients with stage III or IV (GOLD criteria) appeared to have a greater prevalence of reduced LVEF. Our results demonstrated a strong correlation between reduced LVEF and GOLD stage (p = 0.03), as seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Prevalence of Reduced LVEF in COPD and Control Groups.

Parameter	COPD Group	Control Group	p-value
Prevalence of LVEF < 50%	21%	6%	0.003
Mean LVEF (± SD)	52.7% (± 7.3%)	58.9% (± 6.1%)	< 0.001
Reduced LVEF in GOLD III/IV vs. I/II	Associated with advanced stages (III/IV)	Not applicable	0.03

Abbreviations: LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; SD, standard deviation; GOLD, Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease.

Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction

In this study LVDD was measured using E/A and E/e' ratios. We observed higher values of E/A and E/e' ratios in the COPD group than in the control group. Prevalence of LVDD was higher in the COPD group (42%) compared to the control group (19%; $p < 0.001$). COPD patients (26%) also had more advanced LVDD (moderate to severe) than the control group (7%).

Correlation Analysis

After correlation analysis, we found a significant inverse correlation ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.01$) between LVEF and FEV₁ (%). Obstructed airways (decreased FEV₁) seen in COPD were associated with higher prevalence of LVSD. We also found a

positive correlation between the prevalence of LVDD and GOLD stage (Spearman's $\rho = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$).

Multivariate Analysis

In order to find the correlation between COPD and LVD, we used multivariate logistic regression models. We also adjusted for demographic variables and found that COPD was independently associated with increased incidence of LVD (OR: 3.67; 95% CI 1.74-7.76; $p < 0.001$). Age (OR per year: 1.05; $p = 0.02$) and hypertension (OR: 2.11; $p = 0.03$) were also found to be important predictors of LVD, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Multivariate Logistic Regression Showing the Association Between COPD and LVD.

Predictor Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	p-value	Interpretation
COPD	3.67	< 0.001	Strong independent predictor of LVD
Age (per year)	1.05	0.02	Each additional year increases odds of LVD by about 5%
Hypertension	2.11	0.03	Patients with hypertension have roughly 2x higher odds of LVD
Smoking Status	~ 1.00	> 0.05	Included as covariate; not statistically significant
Diabetes	~ 1.00	> 0.05	Included as covariate; not statistically significant

Abbreviations: COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; LVD, left ventricular dysfunction.

Discussion

Our study investigated the prevalence of left ventricular dysfunction (LVD), indicated by

systolic and diastolic abnormalities, in patients with chronic obstructive lung disease (COPD). The coexistence of COPD and LVD is commonly encountered in clinical practice, but gaps exist in the management of COPD with this underlying comorbidity. Study results showed there was a higher incidence of LVD in patients with COPD,

in comparison to controls, even in the absence of a clinical diagnosis of heart failure.

In the study, the prevalence of left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD) was 21%. This is consistent with the findings of a similar study that observed 24% prevalence of systolic dysfunction in COPD patients and 33.3% in COPD patients with concomitant coronary artery diseases.¹⁴ Another study found the occurrence of LVSD in COPD varies depending on disease severity, with prevalence around 10% in all COPD patients but increasing to 44.4% in patients with severe COPD.¹⁵

Our results showed the prevalence of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD) in COPD patients was 42%. The occurrence of diastolic dysfunction was highest in GOLD stage III and IV patients. These findings are similar to that of a previous study, which reported a high prevalence of LVDD in COPD patients (73.3%), with prevalence increasing with increasing stages of GOLD.¹⁶ Likewise, our results showed a high prevalence of diastolic dysfunction in the total COPD population and an even higher prevalence in advanced GOLD stages. This finding is numerically lower than the 90% reported by a similar study conducted on patients with severe COPD. The difference in results is likely due to variation in the study population, given the focus of that study was on patients with severe COPD, while our study included patients at all GOLD stages.¹⁷ Another study found 17% of COPD patients had left ventricular dysfunction with a continuing upward trend in mortality, indicating the importance of cardiac dysfunction in the prognosis of COPD patients.¹⁸ Our study, in line with previous studies, establishes that diastolic dysfunction is a common comorbidity in COPD, with an even greater prevalence in advanced stages. COPD patients require routine cardiovascular evaluation to reduce associated risks with comorbidities.

Further results found FEV₁ is statistically associated with reduced left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), progression of COPD (i.e., higher GOLD stage), and increased severity of diastolic dysfunction. It supports the view of cardio-pulmonary interaction in COPD in which various

mechanisms, such as chronic hypoxia, systemic inflammation, and pulmonary vascular remodelling, are believed to play a role in subclinical myocardial dysfunction. These findings agree with previous studies that express respiratory function measures, such as FEV₁, are positively correlated with left ventricular function parameters like LVEF, meaning higher FEV₁ values are associated with better cardiac systolic function. Lower FEV₁ values are negatively correlated with COPD morbidity and mortality indices, suggesting reduced lung function is linked to increased disease severity and higher risk of death. Similarly, findings correlating the severity and duration of COPD with systolic and diastolic dysfunction have also been reported in other studies.^{19,20}

These findings have a clinically significant implication. Compared with other pulmonary diseases, LVD, particularly diastolic dysfunction, is often left undiagnosed and untreated in COPD patients. This is largely due to shared risk factors and pathophysiological links between the two conditions, as well as the overlapping of symptoms, including exertional dyspnea and fatigue. Patients with moderate to severe COPD and an underlying LVD may experience exertional symptoms or frequent exacerbations. Routine echocardiographic screening in advanced COPD patients is recommended for early detection and treatment of concomitant cardiovascular disease in the absence of compelling clinical signs. Clinical trials and practice guidelines on COPD do not usually address comorbidities. However, management of COPD patients should include the diagnosis and management of coexisting diseases for a more multidisciplinary approach and optimal intervention.

Conclusion

The results of our study clearly demonstrated an increased prevalence of both systolic and diastolic left ventricular dysfunction in patients with COPD, in comparison to non-COPD patients. The prevalence of LVD among COPD patients also varied between stable disease and exacerbations. Cardiac dysfunction was associated with a greater severity of pulmonary impairment,

as indicated by lower FEV₁ values and higher GOLD stage. Clinical symptoms of cardiac dysfunction frequently overlap with COPD. Therefore, extra measures should be taken to avoid the misdiagnosis and treatment of cardiac dysfunction in patients with COPD. Clinical findings of cardiac abnormalities and routine cardiovascular assessments, including echocardiographic screening, should be included when assessing patients with moderate to severe COPD. Early identification and management of LVD can help achieve better clinical outcomes, decrease hospitalizations, and improve overall health of COPD patients. Lastly, additional extensive longitudinal studies are needed to better define screening strategies and cardiopulmonary management of the COPD patient for future practices.

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